

UNIFOOD CONFERENCE

University of Belgrade

Book of Abstracts

Belgrade, September 24-25, 2021

CIP - Kategorizacija u publikaciji Narodna biblioteka Srbije, Beograd

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији - Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

663/664(048)

UNIFOOD conference (2021 ; Beograd)

Program i zbornik radova = Book of Abstracts / Unifood conference, Belgrade, September 24-25, 2021 ; [editors Mirjana Pešić, Živoslav Tešić].

- Belgrade : University of Belgrade, 2021 (Beograd : Razvojno-istraživački centar Grafičkog inženjerstva TMF).
- 197 str. ; 30 cm

Tiraž 30.

ISBN 978-86-7522-066-4

a) Храна - Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 47517705

UNIFOOD Conference, Belgrade September 24-25 2021

Book of Abstracts

Published by

University of Belgrade
Studentski trg 1
11000 Belgrade
www.bg.ac.rs,
email: kabinet@rect.bg.ac.rs

For Publisher

Ivanka Popović, rector

Editors

Mirjana Pešić
Živoslav Tešić

Cover Design Layout

Ivana Isaković

Circulation

30

ISBN 978-86-7522-066-4

Print

Razvojno-istraživački centar Grafičkog inženjerstva
Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Karnegijeva 4, Belgrade

Published

2021.

UNIFood2021 Conference

24th-25th September 2021 University of Belgrade

2nd International UNIFood Conference

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Prof. Dr Mirjana Pešić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia – President of Scientific Committee

Members:

Prof. Dr Ivanka Popović, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Rector
Prof. Dr Petar Marin - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Biology, Vice-rector
Prof. Dr Viktor Nedović - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Dr Marina Soković - University of Belgrade, Institute for Biological Research "Siniša Stanković"
Prof. Dr Živoslav Tešić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry
Prof. Dr Bojana Vidović - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Pharmacy
Prof. Dr Jelena Lozo - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Biology
Prof. Dr Ljiljana Gojković-Bukarica - University of Belgrade, School of Medicine
Prof. Dr Dušanka Milojković-Opsenica - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry
Prof. Dr Branko Bugarski - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy
Prof. Dr Jevrosima Stevanović - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine
Prof. Dr Milica Fotirić-Akšić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Prof. Dr Slađana Stanojević, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Prof. Dr Aleksandar Kostić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Doc Dr Steva Lević - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Prof. dr Nikola Tomić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
Dr Dragana Stanić-Vučinić - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry
Dr Jelena Begović - Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering
Dr Nataša Golić - University of Belgrade, Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering
Dr Vuk Maksimović - University of Belgrade, Institute for Multidisciplinary Research
Dr Nevena Mihailović-Stanojević - University of Belgrade, Institute for Medical Research
Dr Uroš Gašić - University of Belgrade, Institute for Biological Research "Siniša Stanković"
Dr Tomislav Tosti - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry
Dr Bojana Balanč - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy
Prof. Dr Je Yang - Shanghai Institute of Materia Medica, Chinese Academy of Sciences (SIMM), China
Prof. Dr Farid Chemat - Université d'Avignon et des Pays du Vaucluse, Avignon, France
Prof. Dr Jose Maria Lagaron - Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology (IATA) of the Spanish Council for Scientific Research (CSIC) , Valencia, Spain
Prof. Dr Charalampos Proestos, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens Zografou, Athens, Greece
Dr Didier Dupont, French National Institute for Agriculture Research, France
Dr Linda Giblin, Teagasc Food Research Centre, Moorepark, Ireland
Prof Dr Marco Arlorio, Associate Professor of Food Chemistry at the Dipartimento di Scienze del Farmaco, Università del Piemonte Orientale, Novara, Italy
Prof. Dr Isabela Ferreira - Polytechnic Institute of Braganca, Coordinator of the Mountain Research Centre (CIMO), Portugal
Dr Irena Vovk –National Institute of Chemistry, Ljubljana, Slovenia
Prof. Dr Gertrud Morlock - Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany
Sokol Abazi, Canadian institute of technology, Tirana and Noval Laboratory Durres, Albania
Prof. Dr Verica Dragović-Uzelac – Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, Zagreb, Croatia
Nikolaos Tzortzakis, Cyprus University of Technology, Department of Agricultural Sciences, Biotechnology and Food Science, Limassol, Cyprus
Prof. Dr Dražen Lušić, Department of Environmental Health Faculty of Medicine, University of Rijeka Croatia
Dr Dorisa Čela, Noval Laboratory, Durres, Albania

UNIFood2021 Conference

24th-25th September 2021 University of Belgrade

2nd International UNIFood Conference

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Ivana Isaković - University of Belgrade, Serbia

Nevena Arandjelović - University of Belgrade, Serbia

Nikola Savić - University of Belgrade, Serbia

Dr Ana Salević - University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia

MSc Petar Batinić, Institute for Medicinal Plant Research „Dr Josif Pančić“, Belgrade, Serbia

MSc Danijel Milinčić – University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia

MSc Dušan Radojević, University of Belgrade, Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, Serbia

MSc Marina Kostić - University of Belgrade, Institute for Biological Research "Siniša Stanković"

UNIFood2021 Conference

24th-25th September 2021 University of Belgrade

2nd International UNIFood Conference

The word of welcome

Dear colleagues,

We would like to welcome you to the **2nd UNIFood International Conference –UNIFood2021**. We hope that this gathering will engage not only academics, but also the stakeholders from all the relevant industries and business sectors, serving as a meeting point and a platform for proliferation of new ideas and development of new partnerships.

The first UNIFood conference, organized as national, was established 2018. year as one of the events in honor of the **210th Anniversary** celebration of the **University of Belgrade** that ranked at Shanghai list on 35th place for the 2017 year in subject *Food Science and Technology*. The University of Belgrade has been recognized as a leading international scientific institution by LERU when it was selected to be a member of CE7, an informal network of seven Central and Eastern European universities collaborating with LERU on key research and education challenges. Furthermore, University of Belgrade joined European University Alliance Circle U. Following the European Commission's launch of the European Universities initiative, a group of research-intensive universities has entered into a Memorandum of Understanding with the intention of establishing a new university alliance: Aarhus University, Humboldt University of Berlin, King's College London, UC Louvain, University of Belgrade, University of Oslo and Université de Paris.

We are pleased that you have decided to take part in this mutual conversation, where many will present their recent work, through poster sessions, oral communications or simply by asking questions. One of the goals of this Conference is cooperation between academia and food industry. Food scientists, technologists, researchers, nutritionists, engineers and entrepreneurs will exchange their knowledge about the latest advances in all aspects of food production, processing, sustainability, safety and security, nutrition and health, hi-tech equipment, ethics and knowledge transfer supporting environment. At this meeting, over 200 participants from 23 countries will take part.

Belgrade, one of the oldest city in the Europe, always young, at the confluence of the Sava and Danube rivers, will be your host. At the confluence of new ideas and experiences we again wish you a warm welcome.

Sincerely,

Prof. Dr Mirjana Pešić

*President of the Scientific Committee
of UNIFood2021*

Prof. Dr Ivanka Popović

Rector of the University of Belgrade

UNIFood2021 Conference

24th-25th September 2021 University of Belgrade

2nd International UNIFood Conference

The conference organizers gratefully acknowledge the generous support provided by the following:

CO-ORGANIZER

Република Србија
МИНИСТАРСТВО ПРОСВЕТЕ,
НАУКЕ И ТЕХНОЛОШКОГ РАЗВОЈА

DONORS

WITH SUPPORT FROM

**BIOACTIVITY PROFILING OF VARIETAL WINES AND COUPAGE:
IN VITRO ANTI-INFLAMMATORY POTENTIAL**

Ivana N. Beara¹, Tatjana M. Majkić¹, Ljiljana S. Milovanović¹, Bojana D. Milutinović¹, Ljilja D. Torović²

¹*Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Sciences University of Novi Sad, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000, Novi Sad, Serbia*

*Corresponding author: ivana.beara@dh.uns.ac.rs

There are many evidences that support health benefits of moderate wine consumption. From the biochemical point of view, there is certain doubt: which one is „healthier“, coupage, obtained by mixing wines or varietal wine? Herein we present a part of results related to extensive investigation of biological activities of wines and coupage, showing some aspects of mechanisms underlying their anti-inflammatory activity: modulation of expression of enzymes involved in cyclooxygenase pathway of arachidonic acid metabolism, which are responsible for the production of prostaglandin E₂ (PGE₂) and thromboxane A₂ (TXA₂), important lipid mediators in normal physiology and inflammatory response. In an *in vitro* model of early stages of inflammation (LPS-stimulated human U937 monocytes), potential of *Merlot* and *Cabernet Sauvignon* wines, one commercial coupage and three coupage prepared by mixing base wines in different ratios (1:1 (*K1*), 3:1 (*K2*) and 1:3 (*K3*)), to modulate mRNA expression of phospholipase A₂ (PLA₂), cyclooxygenase-1/2 (COX-1/2), PGE₂ and TXA₂ synthases (mPGES-1/2, cPGES, TXAS) was monitored by RT-qPCR. Analysis of wine polyphenols was done by HPLC-UV/VIS technique.

The most abundant polyphenols were gallic acid (41.1–66.4 mg/L) and catechin (15.3–24.5 mg/L), while malvidin-3-*O*-glucoside (3.1–6.0 mg/L) was leading anthocyanin. Some differences regarding contents of vanillic, caffeic and syringic acids, in addition to rutin, quercetin and piceid were found. Resveratrol was not detected in commercial coupage, while in other samples it was quite low (0.2–0.3 mg/L).

Wines and coupage have ability to modulate mRNA expression in applied model-system: the most notable was suppression of COX-2 mRNA expression by *Merlot* and *K1* (3.7 and 2 folds, respectively). Principal component analysis revealed reasonable separation of samples, particularly *K3*, due to the weakest overall activity.

Obtained results implicate that one interesting strategy in creating new products can be used: finding right ratios of varietal wines to achieve enhanced biological activity of final coupage.

Keywords: Merlot, Cabernet Sauvignon, coupage, inflammation.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge financial support of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No. 451-03-9/2021-14/ 200125).